

Predictive Model For Diabetes Detection

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Abstract— Diabetes is a disease caused by too much sugar in the blood (hyperglycemia). Its diagnosis is long and complex. Indeed, this requires, in addition to blood tests, a complex interpretation. Although blood tests can be carried out, waiting for the diagnostic results can take quite a long time due to the lack of specialists and also because of the increasing number of patients in the care of specialists. Thus, for a rapid management of the disease, it is more than necessary to find a mechanism capable of quickly providing the diagnostic result. To do so, we propose in this article, an automated model of diagnosis of diabetes by machine learning. This model, based on the decision tree technique, offers the possibility of predicting diabetes from non-time-consuming clinical examinations with an accuracy of around 74,45%.

Keywords— Diabetes, prediction, machine learning, decision trees, classification.

I. INTRODUCTION

Diabetes is a disease caused by too much sugar in the blood (hyperglycemia). The number of people affected by this disease in the world has increased sharply moving from 463 million in 2019 to 537 million in 2021, according to the International Diabetes Federation [1][2]. This rapid growth is caused by overweight, eating habits and lack of physical activity. Indeed, undiagnosed diabetes can lead to very high blood sugar called hyperglycemia [3] [4]. However, hyperglycemia sometimes leads to serious complications and even death [5][6]. To detect this disease, specialists proceed by having the patient undergo a blood test. This analysis can take several days or even several weeks. And this mechanism is carried out usually when the first complications arise. This procedure can constitute or generate serious complications. This situation therefore leads to finding efficient and effective technical solutions in order to predict the onset of diabetes. In healthcare, data analytics is a widely used method for processing massive amounts of data [7][8][9]. Also, the progress of technology opens up new opportunities in this field. Would it be possible to anticipate the onset of diabetes to help detect diabetes earlier and appropriately in pregnant women using machine learning techniques?

The objective of this article is to propose a model based on the technique of decision trees capable of detecting diabetes before the onset of symptoms, mainly in pregnant women. This technique makes it possible to present information visually, logically and hierarchically. To do this, it has been subdivided into three (3) parts. The first (1) presents the data used for the development of our model. The second shows the methodology used to achieve the objective. The third part shows the implementation and the obtained results.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Diabetes is a dangerous disease that occurs when the pancreas or the body lacks insulin. Many works on diabetes have been carried out. Indeed, Bréault et al. used the Classification and Regression Tree (CART) approach to show the evolution of diabetes in the United States [10]. As to VijayaKumar et al., they proposed a random forest algorithm for diabetes prediction. This algorithm is able to perform, with higher accuracy, an early prediction of diabetes for a patient with higher accuracy [11]. The proposed model gives the best results for the prediction of diabetes and the result showed that the prediction system is able to predict the disease of diabetes effectively, efficiently and above all, and instantaneously. The Authors Adua et al. used Machine Learning (ML) models to predict the likelihood of a patient having type 2 diabetes [12]. To do this, the authors compared four (4) machine learning algorithms (Naïve-Bayes (NB), K-Nearest Neighbor (KNN),

Support Vector Machines (SVM) and Decision Tree (DT)). Thus, the precision, recall, F1 scores, receiver operating characteristic (ROC) scores and confusion matrix of these algorithms were calculated to determine the performance of the different algorithms. As for H. Kaur et al., they used a machine learning technique on diabetes data to develop trends and detect patterns with risk factors [13]. To do this, they developed and analyzed five different predictive models for detecting diabetes. As for, Soni et al., they were interested in the early prediction of diabetes from a patient. They therefore focused their study on the use of six (6) diabetes prediction classifiers [14].

In view of all the precedings, it is noticeable that a grezat deal of works have has dealt with diabetes. In addition, several models have been used together without however arriving at a more appropriate model in effectively detecting the disease of diabetes. Indeed, people with diabetes still develop serious complications such as kidney and eye diseases, and these risks increase in women, especially during periods of pregnancy. In addition, reproductive hormones in women of childbearing age increase insulin resistance [15], so pregnant women are at much greater risk.

The interest of this study is therefore to propose a model based on the technique of decision trees capable of predicting whether a pregnant woman is likely to develop diabetes even before the onset of symptoms.

III.METHODOLOGY

As part of this study, we used a sample of diabetes data published by the Ivorian Diabetic Institute as shown in Figure 1 below. This set consists of eight (8) preponderant variables in the detection of diabetes and 768 observations

	Grossesse	Glucose	PA	EDP	Insuline	IMC	FPD	Age	Resultat
0	6	148	72	35	0	33.6	0.627	50	1
1	1	85	66	29	0	26.6	0.351	31	0
2	8	183	64	0	0	23.3	0.672	32	1
3	1	89	66	23	94	28.1	0.167	21	0
4	0	137	40	35	168	43.1	2.288	33	1
...
763	10	101	76	48	180	32.9	0.171	63	0
764	2	122	70	27	0	36.8	0.340	27	0
765	5	121	72	23	112	26.2	0.245	30	0
766	1	126	60	0	0	30.1	0.349	47	1
767	1	93	70	31	0	30.4	0.315	23	0

768 rows × 9 columns

Fig. 1. Dataset

The data in the figure consists of the following elements:

- **Pregnancies:** corresponds to the number of times the patient became pregnant;
- **Glucose:** it is the plasma glucose concentration over 2 hours in an oral glucose tolerance test. This is explained by the fact of giving 100g of sugar to the patient and waiting for two (2) hours;
- **Blood pressure (BP):** corresponds to diastolic blood pressure (mm Hg). Diastolic pressure is the pressure of the alters when the heart relaxes. Abnormal diastolic pressure is over 90 mmHg;
- **Skin Thickness (EDP):** corresponds to the skinfold thickness of the triceps (mm). This is the measurement of the folds at the level of the triceps. It is taken 2 seconds after releasing the gripper;
- **Insulin:** corresponds to 2-hour serum insulin ($\mu\text{U} / \text{ml}$). It is the fact of taking the glucose level 2 hours after taking 100g of sugar orally by the patient. Its value is between 60 and 120 mIU/L;
- **Body Mass Index (BMI),** it is obtained by taking the weight divided by 2 times the height of the patient ($\text{weight in kg} / (\text{height in m})^2$). The BMI makes it possible to see the corpulence of the patient. When the BMI is less than 18.5 then the patient is underweight. If it is between 18.5 and 25

then the patient has a normal corpulence. Between 25 and 30, the patient is overweight. At 30, the patient is said to be obese;

- **Pedigree Diabetes Function (FPD):** it is the function that assesses the likelihood of diabetes based on family history.
- **Age** (years)
- **Result:** corresponds to the target variable or class variable. Here we have two (2) classes which are 0 and 1. Class 1 means the patient is diabetic and class 0 means he is not.

These data were simulated with the python programming language in its version 3.9 in the Jupyter Notebook development environment.

IV. MODELLING

As part of the modeling, we use the measure of entropy or information gain. This measure is used at each node of the decision tree. The highest information gain is chosen as the division attribute. Considering D represents the set of people tested and P_i the different classes of that set. Each class is characterized by the pairs $(x_i, y_i) \in P_i$, $i \in [1, p]$ with p characteristics (Pregnancy, Glucose, PA, BMI, EDP, Insulin, FPD, Age) where each input vector $x_i \in \mathbb{R}^p$ is associated with an output value $y_i \in \{0,1\}$. Thus, by application equation (1) allows us to calculate the information needed in order to classify a tuple in the set of diseases y_i . Equation (2) is applied to find the necessary information (after using the symptom attribute X to divide the set D into partitions v).

$$H(D) = - \sum_{i=1}^m P_i * \log_2(P_i) \quad (1)$$

$$Gain(X) = H(D) - \sum_{j=1}^v \left| \frac{D_j}{D} \right| H(D_j) \quad (2)$$

The information obtained by connecting to the attribute x can be obtained by subtracting the result of equation (1), which is shown in equation (2). Equation (1) is applied to the data set only once at the start. Next, equations (2) are applied to each attribute. This approach is presented by the algorithm below.

TABLE I

Algorithm: probability of choosing a node

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1  i: Index of the table;
2  t: An element of the node;
3  N: The size of the table
4  C: The whole class
5  C_(i ): The class i of a node;
6  T[N]: the initial basis;
7  T[S]: the new basis
8  Begin
9  Do
11 read. (T[N],N)
12 For (i=1; i<N; i++) do
13   P(k|t) // calculate the probability of membership of a node;
14   If (in ci) then T
15     T[i]←t
16   Else
17     T[i]←T[S]
18   End if
19 End for
20 While(T[S]<>{ })
21 END.

```

As part of the experiment, the given set is subdivided into two (2) parts. Thus, 70% of the samples is used for training and 30% for testing. The node criteria segmentation hyperparameters (entropy, gini, log loss) and the splitter (best, random) were applied to the model. Then, cross-validation (CV) is performed by dividing the dataset into 5 parts (5-Fold) in order to assess the effectiveness of the model. After training and testing each model, we used metrics such as confusion matrix, accuracy, precision, recall, f1 score to choose the optimal model. Thus, the tree of the following figure 2 was obtained by involving the CART (Classification And Regression Trees), ID3 and C4.5 algorithms in the implementation of the model.

Fig. 2. Decision tree model

Test with the decision tree:

The efficiency of the model was tested through decision trees considering the observations of the following figure 3. Suppose a patient is predicted to be non-diabetic when in fact he or she is diabetic (Case of record 4 in our dataset).

	Grossesse	Glucose	PA	EDP	Insuline	IMC	FPD	Age	Resultat
0	6	148	72	35	0	33.6	0.627	50	1
1	1	85	66	29	0	26.6	0.351	31	0
2	8	183	64	0	0	23.3	0.672	32	1
3	1	89	66	23	94	28.1	0.167	21	0
4	0	137	40	35	168	43.1	2.288	33	1

Fig. 3. Observations from tree verification

Step 1: this step consists in knowing the level of glucose in the blood of the patient by giving 100g of sugar to the patient and waiting 2 hours before carrying out an analysis. If the glucose level is less than or equal to 127.5 then go to the True branch. Otherwise let's go to the False branch. In our case, the glucose level is $137 \leq 127.5$ (False). The left part of our tree is discriminated.

Step 2: is to know the value of the BMI. So, if $BMI \leq 29.95$ then we stay on the left of the tree, otherwise we move to the right. In our case, $BMI = 43.1 \leq 29.95$ (False). The left part of the tree is discriminated.

Step 3: is to know the value of FDP. If $FDP \leq 0.30$ then continue with the left part and otherwise go to the right part of the tree. In our case, we have $FDP = 2.288 \leq 0.30$ (False). We finally get a sheet (decision) with class 1 (the patient has diabetes). We can therefore conclude that the figure of the tree above makes it possible to make a decision whether or not a patient is diabetic.

In order to evaluate the best results, a setting of the hyperparameters such as (The entropy criterion, the Gini index, log_loss, the separator (splitter)) were carried out. Then, the confusion matrix between the actual value and the predicted one in order to evaluate the proposed model. It is determined through the confusion matrix function and allows us to know the errors made by our algorithm. Figure 4 below presents the result of this confusion matrix.

Fig. 4. Confusion Matrix

In this case 1 is for patients positive with diabetes and 0 is for patients with no diabetes. So we have:

- True positives: 46 diabetic patients are predicted diabetic.
- True negatives: the model predicts 121 non-diabetic patients who are actually non-diabetic.
- False positives: the model predicts 35 patients without diabetes but actually have diabetes.
- False negatives: 29 non-diabetic patients are predicted to be diabetic.

Figures 5 and 6 below show the performance report. The best performance is therefore reached when the depth of the tree is equal to 3.

Fig. 5. Performance curve as a function of tree depth

This graphical representation was obtained according to the following ratios:

$$Precision = \frac{True\ positives}{True\ positives + False\ positives} \quad (2)$$

$$Recall = \frac{True\ positives}{True\ positives + False\ negatives} \quad (2)$$

$$F1 - score = \frac{True\ positives}{True\ positives + \frac{False\ positives + False\ negatives}{2}} \quad (3)$$

$$accuracy = \frac{True\ positives + True\ negatives}{True\ positives + True\ negatives + False\ positives + False\ negatives} \quad (4)$$

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
0	0.78	0.81	0.79	150
1	0.61	0.57	0.59	81
accuracy			0.72	231
macro avg	0.69	0.69	0.69	231
weighted avg	0.72	0.72	0.72	231

Fig. 6. Performance report

- For accuracy, we have a score of 0.78 for non-diabetics and a score of 0.61 for diabetics.
- For recall, the table shows a score of 0.81 for non-diabetics and 0.57 for diabetics.
- For the F1-score we have 0.79 for non-diabetic patients and 0.59 for diabetic patients.
- Accuracy gives a score of 0.72 for our best model.

Figure 7 below presents the learning curve of the tree.

Fig. 7. Tree learning curve

The learning score curve and the cross-validation score curve converge. However, from a data size between 400 and 500, the two curves diverge. This means that beyond a size of 500, adding training data no longer has a significant effect on model performance. Cross-validation accuracy decreases beyond a size of 500. Adding training data becomes unnecessary in this case. We therefore have a good bias-variance compromise when the size of the training data is between 400 and 500. Beyond 500, we are in overfitting because the validation score becomes low while the training score evolves.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this article, we have developed a preventive model for the detection of diabetes. To do this, data from the Ivorian diabetic institute were used, then processed and implemented using the Python programming editor. The model obtained is based on the decision tree algorithm. The model made it possible to predict "and or confirm the disease of diabetes with an accuracy of 74.45%. Although the model gives a satisfactory accuracy rate, some improvements in the accuracy rate remain to be taken into account. While combining other techniques such as decision trees and Baye's theorem to improve this score.

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